

10929
A3 TRANSMISSION & DISTRIBUTION EQUIPMENT
PS1: SYSTEM ENHANCEMENT, MARKETS AND REGULATION

Emission-free 420 kV life-tank circuit-breaker

Mark KUSCHEL*
Siemens Energy
Germany
mark.kuschel@
siemens-energy.com

Minh NGUYEN
RTE
France
ngoc-minh.nguyen@
rte-france.com

Guilhem BLANCHET
Statnett
Norway
guilhem.blanchet@
statnett.no

Lukas BINNER
Siemens Energy
Germany
lukas.binner@
siemens-energy.com

Maurice Lesser
Siemens Energy
Germany
maurice.lessers@
siemens-energy.com

Radu-Marian CERNAT
Siemens Energy
Germany
radu-marian.cernat@
siemens-energy.com

SUMMARY

Currently, SF₆ is the most used arc-quenching and insulating gas in transmission and distribution (T&D) equipment. However, SF₆ is also the strongest greenhouse gas known, with a global warming potential (GWP) of 24,300 times higher than CO₂ and can persist in the atmosphere for over 1,000 years [1]. Even with leakage rates below 0.1% per year in modern T&D equipment, SF₆ still contributes to global warming, if released into atmosphere. The industry is phasing out SF₆ in distribution and transmission levels to support societies' net-zero targets.

This paper presents and discusses work from an EU co-funded project, MISSION, that aligns with the latest EU regulations. The paper focuses on the work packages related to the development and piloting of a greenhouse gas-free 420 kV live-tank circuit breaker utilizing vacuum switching and N₂/O₂ insulation technology with GWP = 0.

The paper assess, using Norway as an example the potential emission reductions if products with GWP < 1 are used for future grid expansion and replacements in line with the EU regulation. The article delve into the specific requirements and considerations necessary for phasing out SF₆ from the perspective of grid operators. The paper also presents detailed specifications and dimensions of the new product, highlighting its innovative design and operational capabilities.

Furthermore, an overview is provided of the current status of the development tests completed for the F-gas free 420 kV LT VCB, which provide information on the performance and reliability of the circuit-breaker under various operating conditions. In addition to the technical aspects, the article outlines the planned activities for the two pilot projects in France and Norway, detailing the timelines, objectives, and expected outcomes. These pilot installations will serve as important case studies for evaluating the effectiveness of the new technology in real-world applications.

KEYWORDS

Sustainability, MV, HV, AIS, GIS, Natural-origin gas, SF₆-free, F-gas-free, GHG emission

1 Introduction

Since the 1960s, Sulphur Hexafluoride (SF₆) has been an integral part of the power sector due to its advantageous technical properties. However, growing concerns about its environmental impact, particularly in relation to climate change, have emerged. The Kyoto Protocol recognized SF₆ as one of six greenhouse gases in 1997, which spurred further investigation into its environmental effects. As a result, there has been a global push to regulate and phase out SF₆.

In 2024, the G7 committed to eliminating SF₆ from new installations by 2035 [2]. In line with this, the European Union's fluorinated (F-)gas regulation 2024/573, effective March 11, 2024, prohibit or limit the use of new switchgear that contains F-gases with a Global Warming Potential (GWP) above 1. In other parts of the world, restrictions on F-gases have also been placed or are currently under discussion, for details see [3, 4]. In response to growing concerns about greenhouse gas emissions and net zero targets, the industry and electricity grid operators successfully developed and commissioned the first SF₆-free products in the 2010s. Currently, all portfolio gaps are gradually being closed to offer F-gas-free products in good and timely time ahead of the ban dates in EU and other countries [4, 5].

Additionally, there is an EU restriction proposal to restrict Per- and Polyfluorinated Substances (PFAS) - so called forever chemicals. Any substance that contains at least one fully fluorinated methyl (CF₃-) or methylene (-CF₂-) carbon atom (w/o any H/Cl/Br/I attached to it) is in focus. For switchgears, intentionally added PFAS like in fluoropolymers (e.g. PTFE), PFAS F-gases (e.g. C₄-FN) and lubricants are in the centre of attention [6, 7]. Currently, the proposal and the public consultation feedback is reviewed by the European Chemicals Agency (ECHA) assessment committees and a final consultation is to come. The EU PFAS Regulation with its ban is expected to come into force possibly in two to three years, with the first bans in the switchgear sector expected in 2028-2029, should the proposed ban be confirmed. This timeline precedes the existing ban laws in the US states of Maine and Minnesota of PFAS including industrial applications [4].

To facilitate this transition, the EU is co-funding developments aimed at replacing PFAS and SF₆ through the [Horizon](#) and [Life](#) programs. These initiatives promote sustainable alternatives that mitigate environmental and health risks. By investing innovative solutions, the EU seeks to enhance chemical safety, support the shift towards a circular economy, and achieve its climate and environmental objectives. For SF₆- and PFAS-alternatives, the switchgear manufacturer of this paper is currently involved in the “[Horizon Europe Project MISSION](#)” and the “[LIFE Blue Project GIS 420 kV](#)”, see Figure 1. In this paper, the MISSION work packages featuring for the first time an emission-free 420 kV live-tank circuit breaker that utilizes vacuum switching (LT VCB) and N₂/O₂ (called clean air) insulation technology development and their grid operational pilot applications. For the shown DC GIS, the components from the existing SF₆ portfolio will be replaced for the first time by new greenhouse gas-free N₂/O₂ modules, Figure 2 [8]. In addition to MISSION and with view on the emerging market for HVDC grid technologies, a HV DCCB is under development featuring a modular semiconductor technology for ultra-fast DC fault separation.

Figure 1 - Overview of the EU co-funded projects supporting GWP < 1 and PFAS-free transmission developments & pilots of this paper HV manufacturer, promoting sustainability & the latest EU switchgear regulations

Schematic typical bay contains 6 modules

Modules:

- Voltage measurement (RC divider)
- Current measurement (Zero-flux)
- Surge arrester
- Disconnecter and earthing switches
- Cable and Transformer direct connection
- Gas-to-air bushing

Figure 2 – Overview of the emission-free N₂/O₂ 550 kV DC GIS

2 EU Project MISSION

The project MISSION aims to develop and demonstrate key greenhouse gas-free switchgear components for future AC and DC systems, facilitating emission-free energy transmission in a sustainable electric grid. Running from 2024 to 2028 and co-funded by the European Union through Horizon Europe, Figure 3. MISSION will create, type-test, and showcase three essential switchgear components that eliminate SF₆, addressing important technology gaps for both AC and DC grids. In addition to HV components presented in Figure 1 and Figure 2, an ultra-fast 12 kV MVDC circuit breaker for future MVDC grids will be developed.

The project will also assess the technical properties of various SF₆ alternatives for MV and HV switchgear, focusing on scientific challenges like discharge mechanisms and electrical properties. This research aims to accelerate the adoption of N₂/O₂/CO₂-based mixtures in switchgear applications.

Furthermore, MISSION will explore the strengths and challenges of the future European grid, examining the environmental, economic, and regulatory implications of replacing SF₆ switchgears. This transition presents significant technological challenges but offers substantial practical and economic benefits for transmission system operators (TSOs) and grid owners. By developing scenarios for Europe’s future grid, MISSION will analyse resilience, costs, and environmental impacts, providing a roadmap for an SF₆-free European grid and recommendations for EU regulators.

Figure 3 -Overview MISSION timeline, working packages (WP), partners and locations

Finally, MISSION will facilitate the successful rollout of the developed SF₆-free technologies in collaboration with key stakeholders to ensure technical acceptance. The consortium comprises 12 partners from 9 countries, including 5 universities and research institutes, 2 switchgear manufacturers, 4 grid operators, and 1 superconducting DC system developer, Figure 3. The project comprises 14 sub-projects, with SINTEF Energi AS responsible for overall project management.

3 Potential impact on global CO₂ emissions

The European Horizon Mission Project aims also to evaluate the transmission and distribution potential reductions in CO₂ emissions across Europe that can be achieved through the adoption of greenhouse gas-free products in line with the EU F-gas regulation. To this end, two principal primary scenarios are being analysed for the replacement of MV and HV equipment currently utilizing SF₆ gas:

1. "Business as Usual": This scenario involves replacing aging equipment after its typical operational lifespan of 40 years.
2. "SF₆-free by 2050": This scenario envisions a complete transition to greenhouse gas-free alternatives by the year 2050 in line with the European net zero ambition.

Both operating emissions and end-of-life emissions are being thoroughly examined in this analysis. These two extremely different decommissioning strategies represent the main two divergent primary options available to transmission and distribution grid operators as most of them have to navigate in the transition to more sustainable practices.

In addition to the replacement of existing equipment, the assessment also considers the anticipated growth in electricity demand driven mainly by the increasing prevalence of data centres, electric vehicles, and heat pumps. This growth necessitates an expansion of the electrical grid, particularly as Europe shifts towards renewable energy sources such as solar and wind. This unique combination of replacing existing SF₆ assets and expanding the power grid poses major challenges for grid operators in this century in terms of their financial and implementing capacities.

Moreover, the project plans to evaluate the emissions associated with the production of new SF₆-free products to determine the overall net emission savings potential. Currently, data collection for this assessment according to EN 15804 is underway. This assessment encompasses all "mandatory" environmental impacts of a product, from raw material extraction (often referred to as "cradle") to disposal (or "grave") (module A, B, C), as well as the benefits and burdens that extend beyond the defined system boundaries (module D) [4].

In Norway, this process has already been completed, and initial results have been published in [17]. As of now, Norway has approximately 400,000 kg of SF₆ installed with an average leakage rate of 0,13 % which corresponds to 12,100 t CO₂ equivalent. With the additional assets required for future demands, if these were to be equipped with SF₆, the total amount roughly double to 800,000 kg in 2050. This would result in emissions of at least 24,200 t CO_{2e} per year in 2050.

This is the potential reduction assuming that SF₆-free technology becomes available in accordance with the timeline outlined in the EU's regulations, manufacturer have enough production capacity matching with the operators' projects timelines and is subsequently adopted for replacements.

When compared "SF₆-free by 2050" with "Business as Usual" scenario it is projected that this transition could lead to a 15% reduction in total emissions of 120 t CO₂ equivalent compared to the "Business as Usual" scenario, details and assumptions see [17] This underscores the significant potential for greenhouse gas-free technologies to contribute to Europe's climate goals and reduce greenhouse gas emissions in the long term.

4 Product and pilot's requirements

The development of a 420 kV circuit breaker is technically a challenge and requires careful consideration of different requirements to ensure safe reliable operation, as outlined in IEC 62271-1 and IEC 62271-100. These requirements include insulation capability, switching capacity, temperature management, mechanical stability, reliability and lifespan, safety standards, and environmental resistance. It is essential that beside specific development verification tests the defined type tests according to the detailed IEC requirements are successfully completed.

In addition, it is essential to consider the specific requirements of grid operators and target markets. To provide a comprehensive understanding of the market landscape, a thorough survey of grid operators participating in the MISSION project was conducted. This survey, combined with an analysis of the requirements for products that have been launched in the past, allows to identify the primary market needs for the new product. The findings from this analysis are summarized in Table 1, which outlines the key requirements and expectations that will guide the development and implementation of the 420 kV LT VCB.

Table 1 – Main grid operator requirements

Main product parameters of the 420 kV LT VCB	
Type tests	IEC 62271-100
Rated voltages	420 kV (EU grid code operation up to 440 kV)
Rated continuous & short-circuit current, withstand duration	4000 A / 63 kA, 3 s (next step 5000 A / 80 kA)
Rated frequency	50 & 60 Hz
Leakage rate	< 0.1% p.a
Protection class	IP55
Mechanical endurance	Class M2
Capacitive current switching	Class C2
Inductive current switching	IEC 62271-110
Electrical endurance	IEC 62271-310: Class E2

Furthermore, a set of minimum requirements was established in MISSION as a risk mitigation strategy to address potential technical challenges that may arise during the project's initial phases. This proactive approach aims to ensure that the overall project timeline, which spans a total of four years - including a minimum of one year dedicated to service operation - can be met effectively. Following the type test, the pilot installations scheduled for 2026 will begin to leverage practical experience with the circuit breaker in the grid, accompanied by various specialized investigations and measurements. Two substations have been selected to provide quite extreme conditions for the breaker, as illustrated in Figure 4. On one hand, a breaker will be installed at the Dagali substation in Norway, where it will face a cold environment with harsh climatic conditions, including winter temperatures that can drop below -30 °C, along with icing and snow. On the other hand, another breaker will be installed at the Marsillon substation in France, located near Bordeaux and San Sebastián, where it will experience a warmer climate characterized by high solar radiation, elevated humidity, and a corrosive atmosphere. In both instances, the new breaker will replace an existing SF₆ circuit breaker, demonstrating its compatibility with the existing substation footprint.

For the application, direct connections to overhead lines are planned to validate the two pilot projects, as the likelihood of faults in overhead line applications is significantly higher than in other substation applications. This strategy enables us to gather valuable operational experience when the circuit breaker must clear a fault under real service conditions. Additionally, the rapid auto-reclosing

strategy, commonly employed for overhead lines, presents an interesting operating condition for the circuit breaker. If the project timeline permits, there is also interest in testing the circuit breaker in a shunt reactor application to assess the VCB's capability to handle high transient recovery voltages. A detailed program for site investigations has been mutually agreed upon within the consortium, focusing on verifying the following main key aspects:

- On-site handling
- Gas quality and gas tightness
- Switching behaviour
- X-ray emissions

Figure 4 -Locations of 420 kV LT VCB pilots; Left Dagali in Norway, Right Marsillon in France

5 Dimensions, characteristics and development status

In recent years, there has been a significant increase in the reporting and discussion surrounding SF₆ alternative technologies by both manufacturers and users. Various working groups, such as CIGRE, have contributed to this dialogue by publishing comprehensive technical brochures that explore the benefits and challenges associated with these alternatives [9 - 13]. The primary distinctions between circuit breakers utilizing N₂/O₂ insulation gas and vacuum switching technology, as opposed to traditional SF₆ gas breakers, are summarized in Table 2.

Table 2 – Advantages and disadvantages of N₂/O₂ VCB compared to SF₆ breaker

Gas characteristics

- GWP = 0 ensure the lowest possible CO₂ emissions for the entire life cycle
- Simple EHS measures (Non-toxic insulation gas and decomposition products, Non-PFAS-F-Gas)
- Simple gas handling, can be released into atmosphere without any harm
- Safe from F-gas and PFAS regulatory bans, restrictions and obligations

VCB characteristics

- lower arc energy resulting in less contact erosion and higher switching capability
- Perfect for frequent switching applications up to the lowest ambient air temperatures of up to -60 °C
- good scalability to higher short-circuit currents (no gas compression)
- intrinsic constant arc quenching characteristic for current interruption
- X-ray emission at open contact are below requirements according to IEC 62271-1
- high recovery rate of dielectric strength of the contact gap after clearing and no measures for switching current-limiting reactors, short-line- and transformer-limited faults
- not sensitive to di/dt at current zero for relevant power frequencies 16.7 Hz, 25 Hz, 50 Hz or 60 Hz
- switching capacitor and small inductive currents similar demanding to gas circuit-breakers
- hermetically closed means ...
 - Sealed-for-Life, maintenance free for 10,000 mechanical operations at nominal rated current
 - no interaction with CB internal parts and the environment (no toxic by-products)
- high proven reliability; very good mean-time-to-failure; stable gas and long operation

These differences highlight key performance metrics, environmental impacts, and operational efficiencies that are important for stakeholders in the industry. Additionally, the specific characteristics of 420 kV systems in comparison to the established SF₆ technology are illustrated in Figure 5, providing a clear representation of the advancements and innovations of this development. For those seeking further insights, detailed information is also presented at the International CIGRE 2025 event in the dedicated paper [4] with deeper into the technical aspects and operational experiences of these F-gas-free technologies in MV & HV from different OEMs.

Development is currently progressing at an impressive pace, with the properties summarised in Table 2 and illustrated in Figure 5 having undergone rigorous verification through extensive simulations and development tests. The core design of both the breaker and the vacuum interrupter has been successfully validated, particularly in terms of crucial dielectric strength and switching performance. All critical aspects have been demonstrated in a series of tests, with some exemplary impressions showcased in Figure 6.

Figure 5 - F-gas-free LT VCB versus Gas-Breaker

Figure 6 – Exemplary illustrations of the 420 kV F-gas-free tests at Pehla and Kema, from Left: Dielectric, Mechanical Endurance, 2 x High-Power

In high-voltage vacuum interrupters, the post-arc currents observed after successful current interruption tend to be higher than that encountered in SF₆ gas interrupter units. Under certain switching conditions, especially if the post-arc current is very high, this can affect the voltage distribution in a double-break interrupter with standard grading capacitors. To prevent the influence in these rare limiting cases, voltage-limiting elements such as nonlinear resistors can be connected in parallel to the interrupter units (additionally to the grading capacitors) to prevent the overloading of one of the interrupter units in the double-break system [14 - 16].

Hereby, the nonlinear resistors are designed so that they remain non-conductive under the grid's rated voltage, ensuring that they do not affect the normal operating conditions. The conductive range of the nonlinear resistor is achieved only under exceptional conditions, such as during the highest current interruptions and within the brief period at the peak of the transient recovery voltage following a successful interruption, when an asymmetric voltage distribution may occur. In this case, the nonlinear resistors support the equalization of the voltage across the interrupter units. Figure 7 exemplify the behaviour during a 100 % symmetrical short-circuit current (T100s (b)) and an 100 % asymmetrical short-circuit current (T100a) interruption test to present the nonlinear resistors advantage in case of an asymmetrical current interruption. The measurements prove that only in the case of the T100a the nonlinear resistors are needed to prevent an intense asymmetric voltage distribution across both interrupter units. The influence of that voltage-limiting elements is discussed and presented in more detail in [16].

Figure 7 – Successful short-circuit interruption measurements with the F-gas free 420 kV/63 kA VCB [16],
Upper graphs: total current, total voltage, voltage across each VI,
Lower graphs: currents of each grading capacitor (I_C), currents of each nonlinear resistor (I_{NR})
Left: symmetrical T100s (b), Right: asymmetrical T100a

While the fundamental design has proven effective, the manufacturers R&D team is still engaged in minor design optimizations aimed at enhancing thermal management and improving the mechanical durability for continuous switching operations. These refinements are essential to ensure the long-term reliability and efficiency of the system under various operational conditions.

Looking ahead, the MISSION team is excited to announce that the commencement of type testing is scheduled for end of 2025 / beginning of 2026. This phase will be important in confirming the performance and safety standards of the final product, paving the way for its planned deployment pilots and in real-world applications. The team remain committed to delivering a high-quality solution that meets the demands of our industry partners and end-users.

6 Conclusion and Outlook

Global efforts are underway to reduce greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, with the goal of achieving net-zero emissions. Due to the extremely high global warming potential (GWP) of sulphur hexafluoride (SF_6) with $\text{GWP} = 24,300$, manufacturers and grid operators are increasingly adopting SF_6 -free equipment to align with local and international climate targets.

Innovation and regulation are driving decarbonisation and sustainability. EU supports the transition, in line with the latest regulation like the ban on fluorine (F-)gases with GWP > 1 within the F-gas regulation 2024/573, by co-funding the R&D ‘EU Project MISSION’ initiated by 12 partners. This initiative address research and product gaps related to phasing out SF₆ by developing F-gas-free solutions with GWP = 0 in both medium and high voltage AC and DC applications, accompanied by real-world pilot projects in Europe to proceed from 2024 to 2028.

The collaboration within the project and consortium is characterized by a spirit of openness and very constructive dialogue, which is vital to effectively fosters creativity and innovation, allowed to explore new ideas and solutions with enthusiasm and shared purpose. As a result, all work packages and tasks are on schedule and very good quality.

Regarding the zero-emission F-gas-free 420 kV AIS LT presented in detail in this paper, the design has already been successfully validated through simulation and testing. Currently, all preparations are in place to commence type testing end of 2025/beginning 2026, followed by pilot starts in 2026.

7 Acknowledgement

The MISSION project is co-funded by the European Union under the [Horizon Europe](#) program under grant agreement no 101135484 (EU project MISSION).

8 References

- [1] Chris Smith et al “The Earth’s Energy Budget, Climate Feedbacks and Climate Sensitivity - Supplementary Material”, 7SM, IPCC AR6, 2023
- [2] G7 Italia, Climate, Energy and Environment Ministers, [Meeting Communiqué](#), Torino, April 29-30, 2024
- [3] [EU F-Gas Regulation](#) 2024/573, 07.02.2024
- [4] Mark Kuschel et al., Emission-free natural-origin gas alternatives to SF₆ for MV and HV substations, Six MV & HV OEM paper, Cigre Symposium Canda 20025
- [5] Mark Kuschel et al, PODIUM DISCUSSION “EU F-Gas Regulation – 9 month to first ban”, Cigre B3/A3 Colloquium, March 2025
- [6] ECHA, Submitted restrictions under consideration, ANNEX XV, Proposal for [PFASs Restriction](#), 22.03.2023
- [7] Commissioner-designate Jessika Roswall; EU Plans 2025 REACH Regulation Revision: Enhanced Chemical Safety and PFAS Restrictions, [GHS-Report](#), 11-2024
- [8] Maria Kosse et al, Experience with HVDC GIS application during commissioning and early operation phase; Cigre Session, B3 ID 11036, Paris 2024
- [9] [CIGRE TB 589](#), The Impact of the Application of Vacuum Switchgear at Transmission Voltages, 2014
- [10] [CIGRE TB 730](#), Dry air, N₂, CO₂, and N₂/SF₆ mixtures for gas-insulated systems, e-cigre.org, 2018
- [11] [CIGRE TB 802](#), Application of non-SF₆ gases or gas-mixtures in medium and high voltage gas-insulated switchgear, e-cigre.org, 2020
- [12] [CIGRE TB 849](#), Electric performance of new non- SF₆ gases and gas mixtures for gas-insulated systems, 2021
- [13] [CIGRE TB 871](#), Current Interruption in SF₆-free Switchgear, e-cigre.org, 2022
- [14] P. G. Nikolic et al., Basic aspects of switching with series-connected vacuum interrupter units in high-voltage metal-enclosed and live tank arrangements, Paper A3-112; Cigre Paris 2020
- [15] T. Goebels et al., Investigation of the Switching Behaviour, Voltage Distribution and Post-Arc Current of series-connected Vacuum Interrupter Units for Live Tank and Dead Tank Circuit Breakers ≥ 420 kV, Cigre Paris 2022
- [16] T. Heinz et al., Invest. on High-Power Switching with Series-Connected Vacuum Interrupters, ISDEIV, 09/2025
- [17] Thomas Treider, Salvatore D’Arco,;Estimating the Present-Day and Future Norwegian Circuit Breaker Population, Paper 1329 CIGRE symposium 2025 Trondheim